

Low-Set Ears: A New Marker of Fetal Chromosomal Anomalies

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Keywords

Fetal ear · Low-set ear · Aneuploidy · Fetal ultrasonography · Cohort study

Abstract

Introduction: The aim of this study was to assess the clinical utility of low-set ears (LSE) as a novel 2D-ultrasound marker for the prenatal detection of chromosomal anomalies. **Methods:** A multicenter cohort study including 1,331 singleton pregnancies between 11+2 and 34+6 weeks of gestation was conducted in the two participating centers to determine the performance of LSE as an aneuploidy marker. LSE was defined as a dichotomous marker using a newly defined axial plane of the fetal head in 2D ultrasound. Intra- and interobserver variability were assessed to ensure marker reliability. Efficacy in predicting chromosomal anomalies was assessed using LSE alone or in combination

with aneuploidy screening. **Results:** A new axial plane of the fetal head, defined by both lenses and the cerebellum, was adopted for LSE detection. Intra-observer concordance Kappa index for LSE measurement was 1.0, and 0.82 for interobserver reliability. LSE could be assessed in 99% of the studied fetuses and was detected in 30 (2.3%) fetuses: in 19 (86%) of the 22 fetuses with chromosomal anomalies, in all cases (5/5, 100%) with other genetic anomalies, and in six (18%) of the 34 malformed fetuses without a genetic disorder. In one (3.3%) of the fetuses, LSE was not confirmed postnatally while the remaining 29 fetuses had an adverse outcome. When LSE was combined with aneuploidy screening, the detection rate of chromosomal anomalies remained the same and specificity increased from 89% to 100%. **Conclusions:** Our study supports using LSE as a potential 2D-ultrasound marker for chromosomal anomaly detection. Studies with a larger

sample size and in high-risk populations are warranted to prove its clinical utility before this marker can be included in prenatal screening protocols.

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Introduction

In 1985, the nuchal fold was identified in second-trimester fetuses as the first sonographic marker for the detection of Down syndrome by Benacerraf et al. [1]. Subsequently, other second-trimester markers were described, such as hypoplastic or absent nasal bone, aberrant right subclavian artery, ventriculomegaly, echogenic bowel, mild hydronephrosis, cardiac echogenic focus, short humerus, and short femur [2, 3]. In the first trimester, the combined test uses the nuchal translucency measurement in trisomy risk estimation together with biochemical markers. Other first-trimester markers have been described that can be used to modify the risk obtained at the combined screening, such as absent nasal bone, abnormal ductus venosus flow, and tricuspid regurgitation [4–8].

The pediatric and pathological definitions of low-set ears (LSEs) rely on finding the upper tip of the ear helix below the imaginary line that joins the middle part of the orbits [9]. It is well established that in children with Down syndrome, there is a high frequency of abnormal ears; they are shorter, poorly rotated, and LSEs [9–14]. Some studies have prenatally evaluated the fetal auricle and its association with chromosomal abnormalities using 3D ultrasound [15]. A recent 3D-ultrasound study on fetal ear morphology found that fetuses with trisomy 18 presented with smaller ears, while those with trisomy 21 demonstrated alterations in helix morphology [16]. An artificial intelligence-based model has also been used to assess fetal ear morphology in two monogenic syndromes: CHARGE and Mandibulofacial Dysostosis Guion Almeida syndromes, exhibiting a 73% accuracy [17].

Our group has recently evaluated the usefulness of fetal ear length as a marker for chromosomal anomalies based on a newly developed nomogram in a Southern European population. We found an association between fetal ear length below the 5th percentile and the presence of chromosomal anomalies (odds ratio, OR = 3.7). However, the wide 95% confidence interval (1.09–10.7) underscores its limited clinical applicability [18]. Subsequently, our group focused on LSE assessed in fetal 2D ultrasound. Thus, the present study aims to assess the role of LSE in predicting chromosomal anomalies.

Fig. 1. Correct ear implantation according to pediatric criteria.

Methods

A multicenter, prospective cohort study was conducted to assess the role of LSE as a new marker for predicting fetal chromosomal anomalies. The study protocol was approved by the Research Ethics Committees of IDIAP Jordi Gol (CEIm code: 22/040-P) and by Parc Tauli Health Corporation (Ref. 2022/6059). Between September 2022 and June 2024, pregnant women with an ultrasound scan scheduled between 11+2 and 34+6 weeks – according to Catalan prenatal care protocol [19–21] – at the Sexual and Reproductive Health Care Center (ASSIR) of Sabadell and the Hospital Parc Tauli were invited to participate.

Exclusion criteria included: (a) nonviable pregnancy at the time of ultrasound evaluation, (b) aneuploidy screening not performed, (c) multiple gestation, and (d) incomplete perinatal follow-up. The gestational age was established using the fetal crown-rump length measurement between 11 weeks + 1 day and 13 weeks + 6 days. When the booking scan was performed at 14–23 weeks, the gestational age was determined according to the fetal biparietal diameter [22].

Defining LSEs

According to the pediatric definition, LSE are defined as those with the upper tip of the ear being located below an imaginary line connecting the midpoints of the orbits

in a frontal facial view (shown in Fig. 1). Unfortunately, a fetal face's frontal plane with 2D ultrasound does not allow the simultaneous visualization of the orbits and ears. Therefore, a new 2D-ultrasound view was sought that could detect LSE with the aid postmortem studies in the first trimester and of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) in the second trimester.

Intra- and Interobserver Variability

The sonologist team was formed by seven sonologists with expertise in prenatal ultrasound, five from Sabadell ASSIR and two from the Parc Tauli Hospital. Ultrasound examinations were performed in 2D ultrasound with a Voluson S8 ultrasound machine (General Electric) and a Canon Aplio i700, respectively, using a 2–7 MHz convex abdominal probe or a 6 MHz vaginal probe. A single LSE assessment was recorded in each gestation.

A random selection of 66 fetal ear images was used to assess the intra- and interobserver variability using the Kappa concordance index. Three sonologists independently evaluated the same image 3 times at different time points (test-retest 1-retest 2) to assess intra-observer reliability. Additionally, each image was evaluated by three different sonologists to determine interobserver reliability.

Efficacy as an Aneuploidy Marker

Data on aneuploidy screening (first-trimester combined test or second-trimester biochemical screening), genetic diagnostic testing (karyotype, array-CGH [comparative genomic hybridization], exome sequencing, and molecular studies), and perinatal outcome (healthy newborn/chromosomal anomaly/other genetic disorder/fetal structural anomaly, spontaneous pregnancy loss, or termination of gestation) were recorded. To assess the LSE accuracy in the detection of chromosomal anomalies, the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) were calculated. In addition, these parameters were calculated for routine aneuploidy screening and in combination with LSE.

Results

Description of the New LSE Prenatal Plane

In the initial part of the study, we established an axial fetal head view in 2D ultrasound as the best plane to ensure accurate visualization of key anatomical structures, orbits, and ears for LSE assessment. We assumed

that the lens signals the orbits' midpoint and was adopted as the anterior brain hallmark. In the search for the posterior brain hallmark, two methodologies were used: fetal necropsy studies in the first trimester (shown in Fig. 2) and MRI in the second and third trimesters (shown in Fig. 3). At MRI, the upper part of the vermis and cerebellar hemispheres were found to be the posterior hallmark of the axial plane of the fetal head defined by the orbits and lenses clearly visualized anteriorly. During the first trimester, the cerebellum displays a distinct morphology due to the incomplete development of the vermis; however, its upper part was also found to be the best hallmark for the axial plane, according to pathology studies.

In this axial view, a normal upper tip of the fetal earlobe appears as an echogenic line corresponding to the cartilage of the helix. During the first trimester, this cartilage is visualized as two parallel echogenic lines, resembling an "equal" sign. LSE was present when the upper portion of the ear was not visible within this newly defined axial plane (shown in Fig. 4).

Reliability Analysis

The intra-observer agreement presented a 1.0 Kappa index with a narrow confidence interval (95% CI: 0.86–1.14), indicating an excellent agreement. As for interobserver agreement, the Kappa index was 0.82 (95% CI: 0.68–0.96), indicating an almost perfect agreement.

Efficacy of LSE as a Marker of Aneuploidy

Among 1,331 studied fetuses, complete data were obtained in 1,308 (shown in Fig. 5). The gestational age distribution of the studied fetuses was the following: 50% of cases were in the first trimester (11+2 to 13+6 weeks), 32% in the second trimester (14–24 weeks), and 18% in the third trimester (25–34 weeks). Among 1,308 studied fetuses, 1,243 (95%) resulted in a healthy newborn; 22 (1.7%) had a chromosomal anomaly; 34 (2.8%) were structurally abnormal fetuses with no apparent genetic anomaly; four were stillbirths (all due to chorioamnionitis, two in the mid-trimester and two in the third trimester – one caused by cytomegalovirus infection and the other by placental abruption); and five (0.4%) had other genetic disorders. The chromosomal anomalies comprised the following: 11 trisomies 21, 6 trisomies 18, 2 trisomies 13, 1 trisomy 16, 1 triploidy, and one 7q22.2q31.1 deletion (9.15 Mb). There were five further genetic disorders: microduplication 22q11.21 (1.43 Mb), CHARGE syndrome, Meckel-Grubel syndrome, mevalonate deficiency, and Beckwith-Wiedemann syndrome (online suppl.

Fig. 2. Proposed axial view in postmortem first-trimester assessment of LSE. **a** External plotting of reference line for axial cut in a 13-week fetus. **b** Histological section of the fetal head at the same level.

Fig. 3. Fetal MRI (T2-weighted single-shot fast spin-echo) showing sagittal and axial views. Parasagittal slice through the orbit (**a**) and the corresponding axial view (**b**) in a 23-week fetus. Parasagittal slice through the orbit (**c**) and the corresponding axial view (**d**) in a 31-week fetus.

Table 1; for all online suppl. material, see <https://doi.org/10.1159/000548946>).

The time spent in assessing LSE was less than 3 min in the vast majority of cases. LSE could be assessed in

99% of the studied fetuses and was detected in 30 fetuses: 14 cases were confirmed at postmortem studies, 10 at neonatal examination, five declined the autopsy, and in one case (3.3%), LSE was not confirmed at

Fig. 4. Proposed 2D-ultrasound axial views for in utero assessment of low-set ears (LSE). **a** First trimester. **b** Second trimester.

Fig. 5. Flowchart of the studied cases.

autopsy. Of the fetuses with LSE, 19 presented with a chromosomal anomaly, 5 had another genetic anomaly, and 6 had structural anomalies with no apparent genetic disorder. There were no healthy newborns among fetuses with postnatally confirmed LSE (online suppl. Table 1). Of the 15 LSE cases with fetal autopsy, LSE was confirmed in 14 (93%). In two confirmed cases, only one of the ears was found to be low-set at necropsy, one of them previously correctly detected by ultrasound (shown in Fig. 6).

To assess the efficacy of the LSE as an aneuploidy marker, the 1,243 healthy fetuses were compared with the 22 chromosomally abnormal fetuses. In the whole

study population, the mean maternal age was 31.4 years (range: 16–46 years). The ethnicity of the vast majority of the pregnant women was Caucasian (84%) (Table 1). There were 51 different origin countries, although most were Spanish (65%). The first-trimester screening was performed in 1,215 (96%) cases, and 50 (4%) underwent second-trimester biochemical screening.

In our study population, an intermediate/high-risk at aneuploidy screening demonstrated a sensitivity of 86%, specificity of 89%, PPV of 12%, and NPV of 99.7%. The LSE marker alone showed 86% sensitivity, 100% specificity, 100% PPV and 99.8% NPV. None of the fetuses with LSE resulted in a healthy newborn.

The combination of LSE with aneuploidy screening yielded the following relevant findings: (a) absent LSE combined with a low-risk aneuploidy screening result was associated with the exclusion of any chromosomal anomaly (100% specificity and 100% NPV). (b) Absent LSE combined with an intermediate/high-risk aneuploidy screening result had a PPV of 100% versus an intermediate/high-risk aneuploidy screening result alone (PPV 12%). (c) When LSE was combined with aneuploidy screening, it did not increase the detection of chromosomal anomalies; nonetheless, it increased the specificity from 89% to 100%. Interestingly enough, all five fetuses with other genetic anomalies exhibited LSE (Tables 2, 3).

Discussion

Main Findings

This is the first study carried out solely with 2D ultrasound for the prenatal assessment of LSE. Our team has defined a new marker of chromosomal anomalies

Fig. 6. 2D ultrasound of a 13-week fetus with trisomy 21 showing asymmetric ear implantation. **a** Axial view of the fetal head. **b** Right ear with its superior margin aligned at the level of the lower jaw (confirmed at necropsy).

Table 1. Women and pregnancy characteristics

Variable	Healthy newborns, N = 1,243	Chromosomal anomalies, N = 22	Total, N = 1,265	p value
Maternal age, years	31.4 (5.7)	34.7 (6.9)	31.4 (5.7)	0.007
Ethnicity, n (%)				0.152
Caucasian	1,044 (84)	16 (73)	1,060 (84)	
Magrebhi	110 (8.8)	5 (23)	115 (9.1)	
Sub-Saharan	70 (5.6)	1 (4.5)	71 (5.6)	
Asian	19 (1.5)	0 (0.0)	19 (1.5)	
Risk at aneuploidy screening, n (%)				<0.001
Low risk	1,102 (89)	4 (18)	1,106 (87)	
Intermediate	95 (7.6)	4 (18)	99 (7.8)	
High risk	46 (3.7)	14 (64)	60 (4.7)	
Ear implantation, n (%)				<0.001
LSE	0 (0)	19 (86)	19 (1.5)	

Table 2. Contingency table of the combination of the risk level at aneuploidy screening with the presence of LSE

Outcome	LSE		Normal ears		Total, n (%)
	healthy newborns, n (%)	chromosomal anomaly, n (%)	healthy newborns, n (%)	chromosomal anomaly, n (%)	
Risk at aneuploidy screening					
Low	0 (0)	3 (15.8)	1,102 (88.7)	0 (0)	1,105 (87.4)
Intermediate	0 (0)	2 (10.5)	95 (7.6)	1 (33.3)	98 (7.7)
High	0 (0)	14 (73.7)	46 (3.7)	2 (66.7)	62 (4.9)
Total	0	19	1,243	3	1,265

Table 3. Diagnostic accuracy of the combination of aneuploidy screening (high or intermediate risk considered positive screening) and LSEs

	Low-set ears, value (95% CI)	Aneuploidy screening, value (95% CI)	Low-set ears + positive aneuploidy screening, value (95% CI)	Normal ears + positive aneuploidy screening, value (95% CI)
Sensitivity	86.4% (71.4–97.1)	86.4% (71.4–97.1)	100% (100–100)	84.2% (67.7–100)
Specificity	100% (100–100)	88.7% (86.9–90.5)	88.7% (86.9–90.5)	*
Positive predictive value	100% (100–100)	11.9% (6.9–16.9)	2.1% (0.5–3.7)	100% (100–100)
Negative predictive value	99.8% (99.5–100)	99.7% (99.4–99.9)	100% (100–100)	*

CI, confidence interval. * None of the newborns exhibited an anomaly.

based on the pediatric definition of LSE. We have demonstrated that it is feasible to evaluate fetal ears throughout gestation with a small increase in examination time. The description of this ultrasound marker in 2D rather than 3D ultrasound allows a broader application. These results demonstrate that this marker has a high sensitivity and specificity for predicting chromosomal anomalies.

Comparison with the Literature

We are not aware of previous studies focused on fetal ear implantation in 2D ultrasound as a marker of chromosomal anomalies. However, some studies have used 3D ultrasound and artificial intelligence to assess abnormal ear features such as ear rotation, surface, and length/width ratio in fetuses with chromosomal and genetic anomalies [15–17, 23].

In 2011, a study focused on fetal ear rotation in fetuses with common autosomal trisomies. Among the 348 fetuses examined before invasive testing, 32 exhibited abnormal ear angles, and 23 of them were found to have trisomy 21, 18, or 13 [15]. In 2019, Sondern et al. [23] reported normal reference ranges for the fetal ear length-to-width ratio, which was calculated in 118 fetuses between 20 and 40 weeks. A median ratio of 1.9 was observed, with a slight decrease as gestation progressed.

More recently, a 3D-ultrasound study evaluated fetal ear morphology in genetic syndromes. Researchers compared images of 50 fetuses affected by syndromes and 50 unaffected fetuses to assess ear size and surface pattern variations. They found that fetuses with trisomy 18 had smaller ears compared with unaffected. In contrast, those with trisomy 21 demon-

strated alterations in helix morphology and differences in the proportion of the concha and auricle. The study concluded that 3D-ultrasound analysis of fetal ears could serve as a valuable tool for prenatal syndromic diagnosis [16].

These studies have demonstrated that 3D ultrasound offers a superior anatomical assessment of fetal ears compared to 2D ultrasound, enabling evaluation not only of their location but also of their proportions and morphology – features that are frequently associated with genetic disorders. However, the LSE marker was specifically designed for use with 2D ultrasound, reflecting the reality that, as in our center, this technology is widely available in facilities where prenatal diagnosis is performed. In contrast, 3D ultrasound is not universally accessible. A key objective of our study is therefore to promote the feasibility of using the LSE marker across diverse clinical settings, providing a practical and accessible tool to support clinical decision-making. Accordingly, we propose that when a potential LSE marker is identified during routine 2D prenatal screening, further evaluation of the fetal ear should be performed using 3D ultrasound whenever possible. An artificial intelligence-based model has been used in the assessment of fetal ear morphology in two genetic syndromes: CHARGE and Mandibulofacial Dysostosis Guion Almeida (MFDGA) syndromes. The model was trained using 1,489 images of ears from children diagnosed with these conditions alongside control samples. Subsequent testing on fetal images achieved an overall classification accuracy of 73%. The results demonstrated an accuracy rate of 76% for CHARGE syndrome, 75% for controls, and 86% for MFDGAS,

suggesting that machine learning-assisted fetal ear morphology assessment could provide a reliable approach for prenatal genetic diagnosis [17].

Clinical Application

This study introduces a novel aneuploidy marker, LSE, evaluated via 2D ultrasound as a dichotomous parameter. The correlation between LSE and necropsy findings in our study was 93%, reinforcing its diagnostic accuracy. LSE has been proven to be a potential aneuploidy marker in this study. It is proposed as a clinical screening tool capable of eliminating false-positive (FP) results in aneuploidy screening, suggesting its usefulness in prenatal screening for chromosomal anomalies. As with the detection of any malformation or chromosomal anomaly marker during prenatal screening ultrasound, the identification of a LSE marker should prompt a thorough anatomical evaluation of the fetal anatomy. This is essential to rule out additional anomalies or the presence of other markers that may assist in providing the most accurate and personalized genetic counseling for each case.

Limitations and Strengths

This study has certain limitations. First, the relatively small sample size of chromosomally abnormal fetuses may restrict the application of our findings to larger populations. Additionally, as the study exclusively uses 2D ultrasound, the results may not directly align with those obtained through more advanced imaging technologies, such as 3D ultrasound or artificial intelligence-driven models. Nonetheless, the primary aim of this study was to establish a marker specifically tailored for 2D ultrasound, given its widespread accessibility and the limited availability of 3D ultrasound in many clinical settings.

We have also considered the potential confounding effect of abnormally rotated or malformed ears in the evaluation of the LSE marker. However, the strong correlation observed between LSE and necropsy findings in our study (93%) reinforces the robustness of our proposal and supports the reliability of LSE as a diagnostic indicator. Despite these limitations, the study offers notable strengths. It represents the first investigation employing 2D ultrasound for the prenatal evaluation of LSE and demonstrates the feasibility of this approach, with only a minimal increase in examination time. Furthermore, the introduction

of a novel marker for detecting chromosomal anomalies is a significant contribution, exhibiting high sensitivity and specificity within the study cohort. The strong correlation observed between LSE and necropsy findings further substantiates its diagnostic accuracy, underscoring its potential as a valuable screening tool for the prenatal detection of chromosomal anomalies. Given that our sample of fetuses with chromosomal anomalies is small, multicenter studies with larger sample sizes and higher risk populations are required to confirm the reproducibility of our findings.

Statement of Ethics

This study was performed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. This human study was approved by IDIAP Jordi Gol – approval: 22/040-P, and by Institut d'investigació i innovació I3PT Parc Tauli – approval: 2022/6059. All adult participants provided written informed consent to participate in this study. Written informed consent was obtained from the individuals for publication of the details of their medical case and any accompanying images. All participants were provided with an informational written document about the study and written informed consent form, which was signed by both the patient and the investigator. This written informed consent specifies that all requested information is required in order to participate in this study and must be provided to ensure the proper conduct and progress of the research. Data may be shared with third parties and transferred to other countries, always for the same purpose as the study or for use in scientific publications, and always ensuring confidentiality in accordance with current legislation (under no circumstances will it contain directly identifying information, such as name and surname, initials, address, social security number, etc).

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Author Contributions

E.B.-M.: principal investigator and doctoral candidate. Responsible for conceptualization, methodology, data collection, formal analysis, and original draft preparation. G.J. and I.M. and C.L.H.: contributed to data collection and participated in

manuscript review and editing. J.-M.M.-D. and M.I.-C.: performed statistical analysis and participated in manuscript review and editing. J.-C.F. and V.B.: contributed to methodology and participated in manuscript review and editing. A.B.: thesis director, provided supervision, validation, and contributed to manuscript review and editing. All authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study are not publicly available due to ethical and legal restrictions related to patient confidentiality. However, anonymized data may be made available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request and with approval from the appropriate Ethics Committees.

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